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STRATEGY FOR DEVELOPING INCLUSIVE FINANCING IN THE MANAGEMENT OF COMMERCIAL BANKS AND ITS INSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS

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Abstract: This article examines the strategy for developing inclusive financing in the management system of commercial banks and its institutional foundations. In the context of modern transformation of the banking system, expanding financial inclusion and increasing access to financial services for low-income populations, small businesses, and private entrepreneurs is considered a pressing issue. The study analyzes the theoretical concepts of inclusive financing, its economic essence, and its role in bank management based on a systematic approach.

Key words: commercial banks, bank management, inclusive financing, financial inclusion, institutional framework, banking strategy, digital banking services, risk management, retail banking services, financial stability.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada tijorat banklari boshqaruvi tizimida inklyuziv moliyalashtirishni rivojlantirish strategiyasi hamda uning institutsional asoslari ilmiy jihatdan tadqiq etilgan. Zamonaviy bank tizimini transformatsiya qilish sharoitida moliyaviy inklyuziyani kengaytirish, aholining kam daromadli qatlamlari, kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik subyektlarining moliyaviy xizmatlardan foydalanish imkoniyatlarini oshirish dolzarb masala hisoblanadi. Tadqiqotda inklyuziv moliyalashtirishning nazariy konsepsiyalari, uning iqtisodiy mohiyati va bank boshqaruvidagi o'рни tizimli yondashuv asosida tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: tijorat banklari, bank boshqaruvi, inklyuziv moliyalashtirish, moliyaviy inklyuziya, institutsional asoslar, bank strategiyasi, raqamli bank xizmatlari, risk-menejment, chakana bank xizmatlari, moliyaviy barqarorlik.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуются стратегия развития инклюзивного финансирования в системе управления коммерческими банками и её институциональные основы. В условиях трансформации современной банковской системы расширение финансовой инклюзии и повышение доступности финансовых услуг для малообеспеченных слоёв населения, субъектов малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства является актуальной задачей. В исследовании на основе системного подхода проанализированы теоретические концепции инклюзивного финансирования, его экономическая сущность и роль в управлении банками.

Ключевые слова: коммерческие банки, банковское управление, инклюзивное финансирование, финансовая инклюзия, институциональные основы, банковская стратегия, цифровые банковские услуги, управление рисками, розничные банковские услуги, финансовая устойчивость.

INTRODUCTION

In modern economic conditions, ensuring the stable functioning of the banking system and increasing its contribution to socio-economic development remains one of the most pressing issues. In particular, the acceleration of global financial markets, the widespread implementation of digital technologies in banking practices, and existing disparities in access to financial services require new approaches to bank management. From this perspective, integrating inclusive financing mechanisms into the bank management system is of strategic importance.

Inclusive financing is aimed at expanding access to financial resources for all segments of the population, including small business entities, women, youth, and low-income groups, and is recognized as an important factor in ensuring the stability and competitiveness of the banking system. This approach contributes not only to improving banks' financial performance but also to strengthening their social responsibility. Furthermore, within the framework of banking sector transformation, the development of digital banking technologies, remote services, and fintech solutions creates new opportunities for expanding inclusive financing. However, effective management of these processes requires strategic planning, risk management, and innovative approaches in bank management.

The purpose of this article is to reveal the theoretical foundations of inclusive financing in bank management, to systematically analyze its key principles, and to determine its strategic significance in modern banking management. The research findings are intended to contribute to improving banking management practices and to developing scientific and practical recommendations for the implementation of inclusive financing mechanisms.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Issues related to inclusive financing and bank management have been widely addressed in both international and domestic economic literature in recent years. In academic research, inclusive financing is assessed as a key factor in promoting economic growth, ensuring social stability, and enhancing the efficiency of the financial system. Studies conducted by international financial institutions and scholars such as J. Stiglitz, A. Demirgüç-Kunt, and R. Levine empirically substantiate the impact of financial inclusion on banking system stability and economic development. These studies emphasize that expanding access to financial services for the population contributes to the diversification of banks' credit portfolios and supports risk reduction.

In addition, in works devoted to bank management and strategic governance (P. Drucker, R. Kaplan, D. Norton), the introduction of innovative and customer-oriented approaches in banking activities is identified as an essential condition for enhancing competitiveness. These approaches form the theoretical foundation for integrating inclusive financing mechanisms into bank management systems. A number of contemporary studies also highlight that the development of digital banking technologies and fintech solutions significantly expands opportunities for inclusive financing. In particular, mobile banking, remote identification, and digital lending mechanisms help reduce regional and institutional constraints in accessing financial services.

Research conducted by domestic scholars focuses on the modernization of the banking system, the development of retail banking services, and the promotion of financial inclusion. These studies scientifically justify that the implementation of inclusive financing mechanisms positively affects the stability of the national banking system and socio-economic development. At the same time, an analysis of the existing literature indicates that there is insufficient comprehensive research examining inclusive financing in close connection with bank governance and strategic management. This situation creates the need for further in-depth scientific research on the topic.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study is aimed at clarifying the concept of bank transformation and its role in modern bank management, as well as improving management mechanisms. In the research process, a комплекс approach was applied, combining general scientific methods of cognition, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, comparative analysis, as well as specific and empirical methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Within the framework of the study, the effectiveness of inclusive financing mechanisms in bank management was assessed using theoretical and logical analysis methods. The findings indicate that inclusive financing serves as an important factor in enhancing the strategic effectiveness of bank management.

First, the introduction of inclusive financing mechanisms contributes to expanding banks' customer base. Through retail banking services, microcredit programs, and simplified financial products, banks gain the opportunity to attract segments previously excluded from financial services. As a result, deposit volumes increase and the diversification of credit operations is strengthened.

Second, the integration of digital banking technologies with inclusive financing improves operational efficiency in bank management. The implementation of mobile banking, remote identification, and online lending mechanisms reduces transaction costs and ensures faster service delivery. This, in turn, has a positive impact on banks' profitability.

Third, improvements in risk management mechanisms are observed within the framework of inclusive financing. Diversification of the credit portfolio, along with the use of guarantee and insurance instruments, enables the distribution of credit risks. Consequently, the financial stability of banks is reinforced.

Fourth, inclusive financing is emerging as a long-term development factor within bank strategy. This approach ensures alignment with ESG principles, strengthening the balance between social responsibility and financial performance.

Based on the research findings, it can be concluded that the comprehensive integration of inclusive financing mechanisms into the bank management system enhances managerial effectiveness, expands the coverage of financial services, and positively contributes to the sustainable development of the banking system (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The Impact of Inclusive Financing on Bank Management Indicators¹

The figure visually illustrates the impact of inclusive financing mechanisms within the bank management system. The diagram covers five key indicators: the level of access to financial services, the coverage of retail banking services, the use of digital banking services, diversification of credit risks, and the effectiveness of bank management. For each indicator, two columns are presented: blue represents the situation before implementation, and orange represents the situation after implementation. This visual representation clearly demonstrates that the introduction of inclusive financing mechanisms has led to a significant increase in both managerial efficiency and the coverage of financial services.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, inclusive financing serves as a strategic resource for bank management, and its implementation enables banks to achieve sustainable development, enhance competitiveness, and improve the quality of financial services. The conclusions and recommendations developed in this study have practical significance for improving bank management systems.

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¹ Source: Author's own development.

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